

1. Introduction

Zoning is a land use regulation tool that divides land into zones of acceptable uses and regulates building structural requirements and population densities (Hirt, 2015; Frew et al., 1990; Pendall et al., 2006). Since its inception (in New York City in 1916), zoning has acted as a valuable (albeit controversial and increasingly divisive; Trounstine, 2021; Wilson & Appiah-Opoku, 2011; Hirt, 2015; Cassola, 2019; Sclar, 2019) regulatory tool, having wide-reaching impacts from the economy to society to human and environmental health (see Supplementary Section S1 for more details). Today, zoning is used in nearly every city and town (95%) in the United States (Hirt, 2015) and in nearly every major city across the globe (Caves, 2005).

While local-scale examples of the impacts and uses of zoning populate the literature (Frew et al., 1990; Malik & Dewancker, 2018; Whittemore, 2019; Fischler, 1998; He et al., 2022), a comprehensive regional understanding of the full impact of zoning is hampered by the lack of centralized and normalized data (Pendall et al., 2006). Few studies have attempted to gather zoning data or assess the impact of zoning over large geographies. Previous efforts, including systematic surveys of metropolitan ($n = 50$; Pendall et al., 2006) and municipal ($n = 2700$; Gyourko et al., 2008) areas, have shown the use and intensity of regulatory zoning varies greatly across the United States. However, surveys commonly summarize descriptive typologies of land use regulations but fail to provide location-specific information that would enable comparison across political boundaries or to analyze local and regional trends.

To reduce regulatory barriers to zoning reforms, broaden public understanding of regulations, and aid in coordinated regional efforts, the federal government and scientific community have identified a need to develop comprehensive national zoning databases (The White House, 2022; Bronin & Ilyankou, 2021). However, given the complexity to obtain zoning information—one must navigate individual local or municipal websites—little progress has been made. Additionally, zoning regulations are established at the local, municipal, and county levels,

and zone types and coding systems are not standardized (Frew et al., 1990), resulting in wide variation from one location to another (Locke & Rissman, 2015). Led by researchers at Cornell University, efforts are currently underway to create a “National Zoning Atlas,” perhaps the most advanced attempt to gather and standardize zoning data in the United States (NZA, 2023). To date, the National Zoning Atlas collaborative includes around 60 academic institutions and volunteer organizations from across 17 U.S. states; however, major efforts are still needed to approach nationwide mapping of zoning.

A novel alternative to the mass gathering of zoning data is the use of machine learning to predict the locations and types of codes using alternative data sources. Recent applications tested various machine learning algorithms (i.e., Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBoost) to predict zoned uses in small areas ($< 16,410 \text{ km}^2$) outside of the United States (Cao et al., 2019; Hou et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2021). Each of these applications relied on non-transferable or difficult-to-access data sources, such as mined communication data (Cao et al., 2019), to accurately predict zones. Within the United States, we found one application in the District of Columbia (177 km^2 ; Nechamkin & MacDonald, 2019). However, this application was intended for use at small (city and county) geographic scales, was limited to residential zoning, and utilized commercially-available real estate data (Zillow, Inc.’s Transaction and Assessment [ZTRAX] database; Zillow Terms of Use, 2022), which is no longer publicly accessible.

In this paper, we ask: Can zoning be predicted at scale? How does data availability (i.e. data completeness) impact predictive model performance? To answer these questions, we create and implement an open-source, replicable, and transferable framework to predict zoning districts at scale using machine learning and publicly available predictors. Specifically, we implement a Hierarchical Random Forest (RF) model (Breiman, 2001; Di Gregorio & Jansen, 2005; Gavish et al., 2018) to develop a spatially complete map of multi-level zoning districts, including core district and sub-district zones, across the fast-growing urban-rural State of North Carolina (USA;

139,390 km²; see next section for more details). To mimic real-world data accessibility challenges, we evaluated two models: one filling gaps (interpolation) within a county (within-county) and the other applying (extrapolating) to a county without available data (between-county). Importantly, to support the recent government call to advance national open and equitable research (The White House, 2023), code, input data, and predicted zoning maps are fully open source (see Data and Code Accessibility Statement).

2. Methods

2.1 Study Area

To demonstrate the implementation of our modeling framework with real-world zoning data, we selected the rapidly-growing State of North Carolina (NC). The State is the ninth most populous state in the country, characterized by rich mountains-to-the-sea geography that exhibits a wide range of political behaviors and policy clustering. Most of the State is characterized by low-density rural and agricultural lands (less than 250 people per square mile; 70 of NC's 100 counties; Vogler and Vukomanovic, 2021; North Carolina Department of Health and Human Services, 2019), but population growth is rapidly expanding the size of the suburban and urban footprint (Sanchez et al., 2020). North Carolina saw the fourth-highest population growth in the United States in 2021 with concentrated growth in major cities (e.g., Charlotte and Raleigh).

North Carolina has roughly 552 municipalities and 100 counties, each of which has the authority to implement land use planning and adopt a zoning ordinance (NC League of Municipalities, 2022). However, state-wide growth management restricts local authority to utilize many growth management tools beyond zoning (Brookings Institution, 2000). In order to better understand zoning adoption in NC, we conducted outreach to each county's planning department or county manager to determine if a zoning ordinance was implemented for the

county or any municipalities within the county (Fig. 1). We found that 20 counties have no county-level zoning but contain at least one zoned municipality that has adopted a zoning ordinance (Fig. 1a). Another 76 counties have adopted county-wide and municipal-level zoning ordinances (Fig. 1a). For the remaining four counties, we were unable to find any reference to a zoning ordinance as of June 2022 (Fig. 1a). However, some counties with no county-wide zoning ordinance do employ other land use management policies, such as subdivision ordinances.

Fig. 1. Zoning data from municipalities and counties across the State of North Carolina. (a) Zoning activity in each county, including a mix of county-wide and municipal zoning (dark purple), only municipal zoning (light purple), and counties where we found no zoning ordinance (light blue). (b) Data coverage as a percent of county area, from lowest coverage (0.9% in Cherokee County; light blue) to highest coverage (100% in Harnett County; dark blue). (c) Parcel-scale zoning data collected from March to May 2022 across 39 counties for training and validation of our models. Data collected so as to maintain a balanced urban-rural split and spanning the mountains to the coastal plain.

2.2 Zoning Data Collection and Cleaning

2.2.1 Response Variable

The response variable of the Random Forest (RF) model is the zoning district, designated in municipal or county zoning ordinances. Each zoning district restricts the types and intensities of land use within the district. There is no national or state-wide regulation on the naming or type of zoning districts implemented. For example, across North Carolina, we found areas designated for commerce (e.g., markets, shopping centers, etc.) classified as “commercial” (abbreviated as “C”, “COM”, or “COMM”) or classified as “market” (abbreviated as “M”). These designations become increasingly important when considering residential districts. Generally, residential districts are delineated by the density of dwelling units allowed in a given area. However, while one county may label an area with a maximum density of ~7.4 units/ha (3 units/acre) as “medium-density residential” another county may label a district with the same density as “low-density residential.”

Contacting each of NC’s 652 governing bodies was infeasible due to time and resource constraints. We allotted three months for intensive data collection from March to May 2022. During this time, we obtained data – both zoning maps (polygon shapefiles) and zoning ordinances (including all descriptive text) – from municipal web pages or by contacting municipal planning departments (sources of data provided in Zenodo dataset; see Data and Code Accessibility Statement). We collected data from 39 counties (26.3% of the total land area of North Carolina) within the three month timeframe, while maintaining a balanced urban-rural split and spanning the mountains to the coastal plain (18 rural and 21 urban counties; Fig. 1b and c).

Zoning maps generally displayed each district’s name or abbreviation (e.g., “commercial” or “C”) as a polygon with no further descriptions or definitions. Zoning ordinances are policy documents (typically in PDF or Word Document format, length ranging

from 15 to over 200 pages) outlining all aspects of zoning regulation including zone district definitions and densities of use. Zoning ordinances across the State did not appear to follow any standardized formatting, so information about specific districts could be spread across multiple sections and while one municipality may provide two pages of detail for one district, another may provide one to two sentences. Given these wide variations, we coded the documents by hand rather than using a text-scraping method. We searched the ordinances for information on zoning districts including abbreviations, acceptable uses, and development density restrictions, and restructured the information into a tabular format. Finally, we merged the tabular data with the spatial zoning maps using common identifiers (county, municipality, and observed zone district; Fig. 2a).

To directly compare zoning districts across sampled counties and municipalities, we reclassified zones into three core districts (*residential*, *non-residential*, and *mixed use*) and 13 sub-districts (*open space*, *industrial*, *commercial*, *office*, *planned use*, *high-density residential*, *medium-high-density residential*, *medium-density residential*, *medium-low-density residential*, *low-density residential*, *agricultural residential*, *mixed use*, and *downtown*; Table 1; Fig. 2b; Fig. 3a and b). This reclassification is solely intended to create a common language to appropriately compare and assess across political boundaries and is not an attempt or call to impose reclassification statewide.

To reclassify, we determined keywords for each class (Supplementary Table S1) and used R statistical software (v. 4.1.1 ; R Core Team, 2021) to search for keywords in zone descriptions and label them with the corresponding district. For example, we assigned the *commercial* district keywords, including “commercial”, “business”, and “shopping”, such that if the observed district was “business” and had a description stating that the intended uses include business and retail sites, we would reclassify this zone as *commercial*. We matched 96.7% of all collected data to our proposed unified classification. The remaining unmatched data resulted from conditional/special use districts, locally-specific (non-generalizable) districts, or missing

information in the zoning ordinance (districts observed in the map but not in the ordinance).

Unmatched data were excluded from the analysis. We conducted a visual analysis of reclassified data to ensure accuracy and consistency across records. The final reclassified zoning data were then converted to a 30-m raster to be consistent with spatial predictor variables (Section 2.2.2).

Of the collected data, over 85% were zoned for residential purposes, with the largest sub-district (*residential medium-low*) comprising 34.58% of the data, while the smallest (*downtown*) comprised only 0.06% of the collected area (Fig. 3c; Supplementary Tables S2, S3).

Fig. 2. Process and conceptual workflow for predicting zoning districts using Random Forest (RF). (a) We gathered zoning district locations (spatial data) and ordinances (documents describing zoned land uses) from municipalities and counties and cleaned and combined these data to create a single, internally-consistent dataset. (b) We reclassified zones into generalized zoning districts (including three core districts and 13 sub-districts) based on allowed uses and development density. (c) We used reclassified zoning data and a suite of predictors to train an RF algorithm to predict zone districts and create spatially complete zoning maps for North Carolina.

Fig. 3. Reclassified (a) core district and (b) sub-district zoning. (c) Percent of collected land area by district.

Note: Color should be used in print.

Table 1. Core and sub-districts hierarchical breakdown and their acceptable uses.

Core District	Sub-District	Definition
Residential	High-Density Residential	High-density residential uses Minimum area of dwelling unit: 371.61–650.32 m ² (4,000–7,000 ft ²) Dwelling units per hectare: 15.38–26.91
	Medium-High-Density Residential	Medium-high-density residential uses Minimum area of dwelling unit: 650.32–1393.55 m ² (7,000–15,000 ft ²) Dwelling units per hectare: 7.18–15.38
	Medium-Density Residential	Medium-density residential uses Minimum area of dwelling unit: 1,393.55–2,787.09 m ² (15,000–30,000 ft ²) Dwelling units per hectare: 3.59–7.18
	Medium-Low-Density Residential	Medium-low-density residential uses Minimum area of dwelling unit: 2787.09–3716.12 m ² (30,000–40,000 ft ²) Dwelling units per hectare: 2.69–3.59
	Low-Density Residential	Low-density residential uses. Minimum area of dwelling unit: 3,716.12+ m ² (40,000+ ft ²) Dwelling units per hectare: 2.69 or less
	Agricultural Residential	Low-density residential uses and agricultural purposes including crops, livestock, forestry, etc.
	Non-residential	Commercial
Industrial		Varying intensities of industrial uses including manufacturing, processing, or assembling of goods, merchandise or equipment
Office		Office, institutional, and business uses including all employment and community service activities
Open Space		Open space and conservation of land in its natural state or recreational purposes
Mixed Use	Mixed Use	Area designated for more than one type of land use. This could include office and industrial, residential and commercial, etc.
	Planned Use	Areas specifically designated for future development. Generally referred to as Planned Unit Development
	Downtown	Areas specifically referred to as central business district or downtown

2.2.2 Spatial Predictor Variables

We gathered 39 publicly available predictor variables (Table 2) to train the Hierarchical Random Forest model, including datasets on population, community characteristics, built environment, and natural environment. All predictor variables were converted to raster format and resampled to a 30-m spatial resolution. Derivatives of predictor variables include measures of area (e.g., parcel area), euclidean distance (e.g., distance to schools), and urban/infrastructure density (e.g., road density).

Given that zoning restricts the density of urban development and the number of housing units permitted in certain areas, we collected population totals per U.S. Census block (the smallest scale of geospatial aggregation in official U.S. population datasets; U.S. Census Bureau, 2020a). We then calculated population density as the total population divided by the area of each census block. To account for changing zoning policies across different jurisdictions, we used official cartographic boundaries, including census places (i.e., incorporated municipalities, unincorporated settlements), urban areas, and counties (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020b). To capture the spatial patterns of urban form, we obtained statewide parcel data (North Carolina OneMap, 2016). Due to inconsistencies in parcel attribute data availability and formatting, we only drew parcel area and distance between parcels from this dataset.

As zoning can also regulate the location of many community services, such as schools and hospitals, we collected spatial vector data, including the locations of railroads, airports, hospitals, police stations, fire stations, and schools from the U.S. Federal Emergency Management Agency's (FEMA, 2005) Hazus Program. We also gathered recreational area information from ESRI, Inc. to calculate the distance to all recreational areas (point shapefile; ESRI, 2010) and to create a binary raster displaying areas with and without parks (polygon shapefile; ESRI, 2014). Because zoning has long been politicized (Hirt, 2015), we sought to include a variable capturing relationships between political leaning and preferred zoning policies; therefore, we included county-level proportion of registered democrats and republicans

from the North Carolina State Board of Elections (2021). We also considered social vulnerability predictors, such as socioeconomic status, household characteristics, demographics, and housing/transportation, as single indicators as well as a composite index (including 16 indicators; CDC's [2020] Social Vulnerability Index).

Transportation infrastructure impacts growth of cities and demand for public utilities (Duranton & Turner, 2012) therefore, we collected the locations of all roads and intersections from the U.S. Census Bureau (2020b). We converted the road data into two rasters, one for primary and secondary roads and another for interstates. Given that zoning restricts density and building structural requirements, information on building footprints serves as an important predictor variable. We collected building footprints (polygon shapefile) from the Microsoft Building Footprint dataset (Microsoft, 2018) to calculate metrics of building area, density by census block, and distance to the nearest building. We collected categorical estimates of mean building heights, by block group (six categories from "low" to "very high" building height), from the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) ScienceBase (Falcone, 2016).

We consider the presence of permanently protected areas as a predictor variable based on proximity (distance to protected land) and as an exclusion mechanism to avoid predicting zoning districts in areas classified as permanently protected. We collected the protected areas dataset (PAD-US) from the USGS (2020). Included protected land classes: easements, designations, and fees. Proximity to the closest water body was included as indicative of the presence of recreation or open space zoning districts; we obtained a polygon shapefile of lakes and a line shapefile of rivers from the USGS National Hydrography Dataset (NHD; USGS, 2022b). We collected land cover and urban imperviousness products from the 2019 National Land Cover Database (NLCD; Dewitz & USGS, 2021), reclassifying land cover into eight main types: water, developed, barren, forest, shrubland, herbaceous, cultivated, and wetland. To further consider the locations of planted crops, we collected data from the U.S. Department of Agriculture's (USDA) National Agricultural Statistics Service 2021 Cropscape dataset (USDA, 2021). We reclassified the data to

a binary raster displaying areas with and without crops. Topographical characteristics describing slope were derived from elevation data (30-meter resolution) from the National Elevation Dataset (NED) digital elevation model (DEM; USGS, 2022a).

Table 2. Predictor variables used in the Random Forest model.

Derivative Source	Data Source	Predictor variables
Population		
Population	USCB (2020a)	Population total Population density
Jurisdictional boundaries	USCB (2020b)	Distance to census place Distance to urban area County designation
Parcel	NC OneMap (2016)	Distance to parcel Parcel area
Community Characteristics		
Hazus	FEMA (2005)	Distance to railroad Distance to airport Distance to hospital Distance to police station Distance to fire station Distance to school
Parks	ESRI (2014; 2010)	Park binary (y/n) Distance to park
Voter registration	North Carolina State Board of Elections (2021)	Proportion of democrats Proportion of republicans
Social vulnerability	CDC (2020)	Social vulnerability index Income index Housing units Number of mobile homes Housing composition Housing transport Housing density
Built Environment		
Transportation infrastructure	USCB (2020b)	Distance to road Distance to interstate Distance to interchange
Building footprint	Microsoft (2022)	Building density Distance to building Building area
Building height	Falcone (2016)	Building height
Natural Environment		
Elevation	USGS (2022a)	Slope
Hydrography	USGS (2022b)	Distance to lake Distance to river
Permanently protected areas	USGS (2020)	Protected land (y/n) Distance to protected land
Land Cover	USGS (2021)	Land cover (water, developed, barren, forest, shrubland, herbaceous, cultivated, wetland) Impervious surface

Agriculture

USDA (2021)

Crop (y/n)

Distance to cropland

USCB = U.S. Census Bureau; NC OneMap = North Carolina OneMap; Hazus = Nationally standardized risk modeling methodology ([fema.gov/flood-maps/products-tools/hazus](https://www.fema.gov/flood-maps/products-tools/hazus)); FEMA = U.S. Federal Emergency Management Agency; CDC = U.S. Center for Disease Control and Prevention; USGS = U.S. Geological Survey; USDA = U.S. Department of Agriculture; y/n = yes/no.

2.3 Model Implementation

We implemented a Hierarchical Random Forest model (staged classification where broad-level classes [core district zones] are subdivided into more detailed subclasses [sub-district zones]; Breiman, 2001; Di Gregorio & Jansen, 2005) in the Python programming language (v. 3.0; Van Rossum, 1995) using the open source machine learning package, *sklearn* (Pedregosa et al., 2011). We also utilized Python's *Dask-mpi* library (Rocklin, 2015) to run the random forest using distributed memory and loaded all rasters as Dask arrays (large data divided into smaller parts to reduce RAM requirement).

To mimic real-world data accessibility challenges, we evaluated two model implementations (Fig. 4). First, our within-county model is designed to represent a condition where zoning data is partially available within a given county, and model predictions fill intra-county data gaps. To test within-county performance, we randomly removed 20% of the data from the training dataset and reserved it for independent accuracy assessments (Fig. 4a; Supplementary Section S2; Supplementary Table S4). Second, our between-county model is designed to predict zoning in counties where no data is available, and the model is trained with data from other counties. However, our data collection efforts yielded data from 39 counties ranging across the rural-urban gradient; with coverage ranging from 1% (Cherokee County) to 100% (Harnett County) of the county's land area. Additionally, underlying differences in zoning patterns—rural counties commonly have few large zoning districts, while urban counties are shaped by heterogeneous, multi-zone patterns—resulted in varying amounts of training data for each zoning district (i.e., class imbalance and underrepresentation of the response variable). Therefore, we conducted 15 random samples where we randomly selected 31 counties (~80% of counties) to train the model and the remaining 8 (~20%) counties were used for independent testing (Fig. 4b). Utilizing multiple random samples allowed us to capture different combinations of training and testing counties and evaluate the influence on model performance. To choose

training and testing data, we used a simple random sampling method without replacement, meaning once data was selected for training it was removed from the test dataset.

Fig. 4. Graphical representation of training and testing datasets for (a) within-county and (b) between-county models. (a) For within-county models, we randomly select 80% of the observed data for training and 20% for testing. (b) For between-county models, we divide the observed data by county. That is, we randomly select 80% of counties for training and 20% for testing. To account for variation in zoning district makeup across counties, we computed average performance across 15 simple random samples of training/testing counties (see Section 2.3).

2.4.1 Model Tuning

We performed cross-validation parameter tuning for three key model parameters (maximum tree depth [*max_depth*], number of trees [*ntrees*], and number of randomly sampled candidate variables at each split [*mtry*]) for between- and within-county models (Probst et al., 2019). We chose one value for each parameter to balance strong and poor performance (assessed using F1 scores) for both models. Where discrepancies arose between model tuning, we chose the parameter that better suited between-county tests, given the greater challenge of predicting between counties. We found that the model performed marginally better with 250 trees, but chose 100 trees to minimize computation time. The Random Forest algorithm operates such that overfitting (i.e., model fits too closely to training data such that it cannot predict for un-trained data) is highly unlikely (Breiman, 2001), and performing cross-validation tuning and utilizing an independent test dataset further reduces the chance of overfitting (Probst et al., 2019).

Ultimately, we chose a tree depth of 25 [*max_depth* = 25], 100 trees [*ntrees* = 100], and six candidate variables [*mtry* = 6].

2.4 Accuracy Assessment

We assessed classification accuracy by calculating each model's R^2 (i.e., R-squared, coefficient of determination) as well as their overall and per-district precision, recall, and F1 score. R^2 measures the predictive power of the model and is used to understand how well the model explains differences present in the data (Chicco et al., 2021). Precision and recall metrics were chosen to compare model performance in terms of under- and over-prediction (Pontius & Millones, 2011). Precision is a measure of true positive predictions made out of all positive predictions (e.g., of 100 residential zoning district parcels predicted, 75 were correct). Recall is a measure of the number of true positive predictions made out of all positive instances in the data (e.g., of all 100 residential zoning district parcels that exist, the model predicted 75 correctly). F1 score is the harmonic mean (number of observations divided by the sum of the reciprocals of

each observation) of precision and recall, and we use it as an alternative to traditional measures of model accuracy (number of correct predictions out of all predictions) to better describe overall model performance (Gu et al., 2009). All metrics are calculated for the testing dataset alone.

To measure each variable's relative importance, we computed the Gini Impurity (a measure of the mean decrease in impurity; percent of variance explained by the model) for all predictors across all models (Fig. 5). The index measures the difference between impurity before and after splitting the data into two distinct groups using a given predictor; the higher the index value the higher the importance of a specific predictor variable in the model (Breiman, 2017).

Fig. 5. Relative variable importance (measured by Gini Impurity - percent of variance explained by the model) for all spatial predictors. Impurity (y-axis) for each predictor (x-axis) corresponds to the sum of impurity measured in each model (within-county core districts, within-county sub-districts, between-county core districts, and between-county sub-districts). For between-county models, impurity is the average of impurity calculated in each of the 15 random samples (see Section 2.3 for more information on sampling).

3. Results

3.1 Variable Importance

We found that voting predictors were the most important variables independent of the evaluated model. Proportion of republicans accounted for an average of 10.49% of variance across all four models and proportion of democrats accounted for an average of 8.60% of the variance. Building height was the third most influential variable across all model implementations accounting for 4.14% of the variance. A total of 21 variables collectively explain 80% of the variance, with the final being distance to parks (accounting for 2.31% of the variance). Protected areas is the least influential variable explaining no variance in any model. Building area is the second least influential variable explaining 0.03% of the variance (Fig. 5).

3.2 Within-county Model Performance

3.2.1 Core District Performance

We found 98.8% overall accuracy, a macro average (i.e., unweighted mean) F1 score of 0.972, and R^2 of 0.929 for predicting core districts for the within-county model. When broken down by district, the lowest F1 score was for *non-residential* at 0.947. This district's recall was 0.907 and precision was 0.991, suggesting that the model slightly under-predicted this district (i.e., predicted fewer instances than observed). *Residential* had the highest recall (0.999) and F1 score (0.993) with marginally lower precision (0.988), suggesting that the model slightly over-predicted this district and misclassified around 10% of *non-residential* land as *residential* (Table 3; Fig. 6).

3.2.2 Sub-District Performance

We calculated 98.8% overall accuracy, a macro average F1 score of 0.977, and R^2 of 0.962 for sub-districts for the within-county model. When broken down by district, the lowest F1 score was for *office* (0.944). This district had high precision (0.984) but the lowest recall (0.908) suggesting the model under-predicted this district. We expect lower performance in the less prevalent districts. This holds true for *office*, the second smallest district by area (0.56% of the area of collected data), however, *downtown* comprises 0.06% of the area of the total dataset and shows stronger performance than *office* (F1 score 0.961). *Commercial*, *industrial*, *open space*, and *downtown* also showed higher precision than recall but with a maximum difference between precision and recall of (0.065). All other districts had balanced precision and recall suggesting that the model correctly classified the data without greatly over- or under-predicting (Table 3; Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Within-county core district model predictions and performance. (a) Observed (current) zoning (note: not current *use*) and (b) predicted core zoning districts shown as purple for residential (includes agricultural areas), pink/red for non-residential, and blue for mixed use. (c) Percent misclassified pixels aggregated to a 3-km grid.

Note: Color should be used in print.

Fig. 7. Within-county sub-district model predictions and performance. (a) Observed and (b) predicted sub-districts for North Carolina. (c) Percent misclassified pixels aggregated to a 3-km grid.

Note: Color should be used in print.

Table 3. Performance metrics (precision, recall, and F1) for core district and sub-district within- and between-county models. Mean and standard deviation (sd) performance metrics derived from evaluating the 15 different random samples of the between-county models.

Model	Core District	Precision		Recall		F1 score		
		mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	
Within	Residential	0.988		0.999		0.993		
	Non Residential	0.991		0.907		0.947		
	Mixed Use	0.996		0.955		0.975		
	macro average	0.991		0.954		0.972		
	Sub-District							
	Residential High	0.975		0.973		0.974		
	Residential Medium-High	0.978		0.989		0.984		
	Residential Medium	0.991		0.986		0.989		
	Residential Medium-Low	0.987		0.997		0.992		
	Residential Low	0.996		0.992		0.994		
	Agriculture	0.989		0.998		0.993		
	Commercial	0.985		0.944		0.964		
	Industrial	0.990		0.955		0.972		
	Office	0.984		0.908		0.944		
	Open Space	0.993		0.928		0.959		
Mixed Use	0.995		0.978		0.987			
Planned Use	0.993		0.988		0.990			
Downtown	0.978		0.945		0.961			
macro average	0.987		0.968		0.977			
Between								
Between	Residential	0.856	0.055	0.986	0.017	0.915	0.031	
	Non Residential	0.729	0.116	0.208	0.075	0.316	0.094	
	Mixed Use	0.245	0.218	0.005	0.005	0.008	0.005	
	macro average	0.610	0.092	0.400	0.026	0.413	0.038	
	Sub-District							
	Residential High	0.278	0.143	0.045	0.027	0.071	0.041	
	Residential Medium-High	0.415	0.121	0.432	0.141	0.395	0.072	
	Residential Medium	0.262	0.132	0.224	0.179	0.185	0.068	
	Residential Medium-Low	0.372	0.209	0.577	0.271	0.425	0.206	

Residential Low	0.070	0.130	0.006	0.017	0.011	0.029
Agriculture	0.085	0.150	0.112	0.226	0.048	0.053
Commercial	0.347	0.098	0.131	0.086	0.167	0.085
Industrial	0.498	0.089	0.134	0.037	0.207	0.046
Office	0.272	0.275	0.012	0.016	0.022	0.029
Open Space	0.140	0.309	0.007	0.014	0.008	0.013
Mixed Use	0.238	0.334	0.021	0.027	0.034	0.050
Planned Use	0.274	0.400	0.003	0.005	0.005	0.009
Downtown	0.578	0.381	0.024	0.033	0.042	0.058
macro average	0.295	0.063	0.133	0.027	0.125	0.020

3.3 Between-county Model Performance

To evaluate the sensitivity of the between-county model to the counties selected for training, we compared 15 separate random samples of counties. In each, we randomly sampled 20% of the counties for testing. We then calculated the mean and standard deviation of precision, recall, accuracy, and F1 scores, overall and per-district (i.e., core districts and sub-districts) across all random samples.

3.3.1 Core District Performance

We found 84.5% accuracy (sd: 0.052), a mean macro-averaged F1 score of 0.413 which remained relatively constant across samples (sd = 0.038), and an R^2 of -0.205 (sd: 0.217) for the core district between-county model. Additionally, we observed strong performance for residential districts with a mean macro-averaged F1 score of 0.915 (sd = 0.031; Table 3). However, we found overall low performance across the *non-residential* (F1 score = 0.316; sd = 0.094) and *mixed-use* (F1 score = 0.008; sd = 0.005; Table 3) districts.

3.3.2 Sub-District Performance

We calculated 28.0% accuracy (sd: 0.090), a mean macro-averaged F1 score of 0.125 which was relatively constant across samples (sd = 0.020), and R^2 of -0.361 (sd: 0.443) for the sub-district between-county model. However, we found wide variation performance when broken down by district. The districts with the highest mean F1 scores also presented the highest variability, as estimated by proportionally large standard deviations (Table 3). *Residential-medium-low* had the highest mean F1 score (0.425) and highest standard deviation of 0.206 (Table 3). The county with the highest misclassification rate varied based on the selected training counties, but counties outside of the training dataset consistently performed poorer than those in the training dataset (Fig. 8; Supplementary Fig. S1).

Fig. 8. Between-county sub-district model predictions and performance for two different combinations of training and testing counties, one including (a) both Cleveland and Brunswick counties in the training sample and another excluding them from the training sample. (b) Observed sub-districts for (b1) Cleveland and (b2) Brunswick Counties. Predicted sub-districts when (c1) Cleveland and (c2) Brunswick are included in training. Predicted sub-districts when (d1) Cleveland and (d2) Brunswick counties are excluded from training. Proportion of misclassified pixels aggregated to a 3-km grid under both combinations of training and testing scenarios (e1 and e3 included in training; f1 and f2 excluded). Note: Color should be used in print.

3.4 Statewide Map of Zoning

To create the spatially complete map of zoning for NC, we used a combination of observed data (where collected), within-county model for counties with collected data, and the between-county model for counties with no collected data (Fig. 9). For this map, the between-county model was trained on all available data but applied only to counties with no collected data. Accuracy of this map varies depending on what model was used (Fig. 9c). Accuracy presumed high in areas using within-county model (98.8% for core district and sub-districts) and uncertain in areas using between-county model (likely around 84.5% for core districts and around 28.0% for sub-districts).

Fig. 9. Spatially complete zoning maps of North Carolina generated from a combination of observed and predicted data using both the within- and between-county models, including (a) core district and (b) sub-district zoning. (c) Illustrates the spatial extent of observed zoning (in dark gray), predicted within-county zoning (in gray), and predicted between-county zoning (in light gray) in the final map.

Note: Color should be used in print.

4. Discussion

4.1 Variable Importance

We compared the variable importance across models and found that 21 variables (~half) collectively explain 80% of the variance (Fig. 5). The exclusion of less influential variables could streamline the modeling process by reducing the requirements for data collection and processing. Among the predictors with lower importance (i.e., candidates for exclusion) were protected areas, building area, presence of parks, and distance to roads (collectively explain ~1.3% of the variance). The low performance of presence of parks was expected due to limited positive instances in the training data. Although we initially anticipated higher importance for building area and distance to roads (Duranton & Turner, 2012), other predictors related to built environment characteristics collectively accounted for 16.60% of variance (i.e., building height, road density, distance to interstate, and distance to interchange). Consequently, the relatively low predictive influence of distance to roads and building area can be attributed to the inclusion of other predictors that likely capture similar relationships, which further supports the potential exclusion of these predictors from the model. Conversely, variables such as voter registration records consistently displayed the highest variable importance (proportion of registered republican and democrats by county together explaining 19% of variance) across all models (Fig. 5). Part of this importance could be attributed to the difference in zoning composition between majority-Republican and majority-Democrat counties. Majority-Republican counties exhibit a higher prevalence of *residential medium-low* zoning (26.4% of the area), whereas this district ranks as the fifth most common district (8.3% of the area) in majority-Democrat counties. More generally, zoning varies widely between counties due to local regulations, and voting predictors used in this analysis were derived at the county level. Therefore, it is likely that part of the importance of these variables stems from their ability to differentiate between counties.

4.2 Model Performance

We developed the first spatially complete zoning map depicting core and sub-districts across the State of North Carolina (Fig. 9). Predictions show overall high accuracy (core districts = 98.8%; sub-districts = 98.8%) for counties with partially available training datasets (i.e., within-county model). This indicates that the model correctly classified core districts for 98.8% of the landscape and sub-districts for 98.8%. However, further research is needed to accurately extrapolate between counties (i.e., between-county models) to make predictions where there is no available (or inaccessible) data for model training. While there are limitations to our approach (see next section), our findings are robust and improve on previous zoning prediction efforts, even when considering discrepancies in accuracy assessment methods, spatial scale, and predictions of specific land use types (Cao et al., 2019; Nechamkin & MacDonald, 2019; Wang et al., 2017; and Hou et al., 2020).

Relative to previous studies, our within-county models showed overall higher accuracy. For example, Cao et al. (2019) showed an overall accuracy of 88.05% using XGBoost and 84.5% using Random Forest to predict seven urban functional zones across the Yuzhong District in the City of Chongqing, China. The improved performance of our model could be attributed to the selection of predictors. In contrast to Cao et al. (2019), where five main predictors were selected including night-time light imagery and social media data, our models utilized a comprehensive suite of 39 predictors, including population and community characteristics, as well as detailed attributes of the built and natural environment. Additionally, our model benefitted from a large training dataset (over 42 million data points), which likely contributed to its improved performance.

Further research is necessary to improve the reliability of between-county model predictions in identifying *non-residential* (F1 score of 0.316) and *mixed used* (F1 score of 0.008) core districts and differentiate between *residential* sub-districts (F1 score 0.011–0.425). Class imbalances resulting from the proportionately larger representation of *residential* districts in the

training dataset (85.45%) compared to other classes (i.e. 14.55% of collected data represents *mixed used, commercial, industrial, office, downtown, planned use, and open space*; Fig. 3c) could explain the variation in performance across districts. Furthermore, we observe lower performance in the *residential* districts in sub-district models, which we hypothesize is attributed to the division of the dominant district into six sub-districts, thereby reducing the amount of training data and affecting the model's predictive accuracy for the sub-districts.

When evaluating the performance of the between-county model on different subsets of training counties (random samples), we found varying levels of accuracy and noticeable changes in the predicted zoning patterns. Figure 8 demonstrates the difference in predicted sub-districts between two counties, Cleveland and Brunswick, when these counties were included in the training dataset compared to when they were excluded. Results predicted in both sampled counties (Cleveland and Brunswick) demonstrate high accuracy in predicted zoning patterns when the counties are included in the training sample (Fig. 8c1 and c2), but dramatically lower accuracy when they are excluded (Fig. 8d1 and d2). In Brunswick County, predicted patterns closely match observed patterns when the partially-complete observed data is included for training (Fig. 8c2), however when Brunswick's observed data is excluded, the predicted spatial pattern is characterized by a more homogeneous distribution of *residential* districts, with small clusters of *high-density residential* or *non-residential* districts along the coast (Fig. 8d2). Additionally, we find high error in both counties as the result of misclassifying *residential* density. When Cleveland County, which is characterized by more homogenous observed zoning and a lower number of sub-district classes, is included and excluded from training, the model captures the observed spatial pattern relatively well. However, when excluded from training, there is a significant misclassification of observed *medium-density residential* zones (Fig. 8b1), which are predicted as *medium-low-density residential* (Fig. 8d1). This outcome was consistently observed across other counties and the 15 evaluated training samples.

4.3 Study Limitations and Future Research

There are limitations of our framework that can be improved in future applications. While our model demonstrates high performance in predicting zoning patterns in areas where zoning data is partially available (within-county or interpolating), its predictive ability is limited in counties where zoning data is entirely inaccessible (between-county or extrapolating). This highlights the need for future research that explores data collection strategies that sample a representative portion of districts from each county for which predictions are to be computed (Sinha et al., 2019; Supplementary Section S3; Supplementary Table S5; Supplementary Figure S2).

Furthermore, given large class imbalances—roughly 85% of sampled zoned areas are restricted for residential uses—additional considerations could be given to sampling techniques (Chen & Breiman, 2004). Future research could also assess model performance over smaller geographies that exhibit high similarities (e.g., counties within the same metropolitan planning organizations [MPOs]). We anticipate that such an analysis could yield satisfactory model performance, considering the observed variation in performance in the between-county tests depending on the selection of training counties.

Our models were trained using zoning data collected in 2022. Zoning ordinances are living documents and changes since 2022 may not be reflected in the current model. However, most zoning updates are targeted and specific to certain areas or properties, rather than encompassing the large portions of the study area (e.g., see Whittemore, 2019; Hino et al., 2023). Therefore, the majority of the zoning data is likely to remain relevant and informative for analysis and modeling purposes. Additionally, this framework could be easily replicated to allow for the addition of new or updated zoning data as it becomes available. Assessing how zoning changes over time and how these changes might affect model performance provides another opportunity for future research. To the best of our knowledge, there is limited research on how zoning changes through time over large geographic extents. While some studies have examined this on smaller scales (e.g., Durham, NC; Whittemore, 2019) or focused on specific zone

transitions (e.g. residential density; Broitman & Koomen, 2015) there is a need for more extensive research in this area.

By necessity, we developed generalized zone districts to compare counties and municipalities across NC. However, this simplification can obscure the subtle differences between areas and can overlook the unique cultural characteristics of smaller towns. Future work could apply this framework to different zone generalizations or smaller areas to offer a better representation of local realities and contexts.

Environmental hazards, including flooding, are intensifying and occurring more frequently due to climate change (IPCC, 2023). Zoning can play a crucial role as a non-structural adaptation strategy to enhance community resilience. For example, the City of Cedar Falls, Iowa, updated its zoning ordinance to incorporate stricter building requirements in flood-prone areas (U.S. EPA, 2017). In future applications, this framework could be utilized to assess zoned land uses and their vulnerability to environmental hazards. Furthermore, in order to effectively address risk, it is necessary to consider the changing urban landscape and how zoning influences the potential for new development (He et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020; Onsted & Chowdhury, 2014). Evaluating the interconnections between zoning and other land use regulations, urban expansion, climate change, and environmental hazards can provide valuable insights for future planning and policy-making efforts focused on enhancing community and regional resilience.

4.4 Applications for Local and Regional Planning

There are both local to regional implications of our findings and data products to inform planning. First, at the local or municipal scale the creation and distribution of open access, spatially complete zoning maps (see Data and code accessibility) could reduce the “benchmarking” workload of planning departments across North Carolina. Benchmarking is a laborious and time-consuming process that involves gathering zoning data from nearby or similar municipalities when creating or updating a zoning ordinance. It typically involves contacting

individual municipalities, collecting maps and zoning ordinances, and comparing them to the current implementation. By leveraging our predicted zoning maps, planners will have the ability to quickly identify zoning patterns across the State, eliminating the need for the laborious process of gathering and analyzing disparate data sources and formats. However, accuracy of predicted maps must be clearly communicated and ground-truthing is recommended. Ultimately, these predicted zoning maps could particularly benefit small, rural, and/or under-resourced communities seeking to enact or improve their land use regulations by providing a starting point for practitioners.

At the regional scale, the coordination of zoning regulations across regions is recommended to promote economic growth, equity, sustainability, and climate resiliency. This coordination is essential for ensuring the long-term productive growth of cities and achieving local and statewide planning goals (American Planning Association, 2022). Zoning has great potential as a non-structural adaptation strategy to prevent risky development and promote the sustainable growth of cities in the face of an uncertain climate (U.S. EPA, 2017; Hino et al., 2023). For instance, in the aftermath of Superstorm Sandy, New York City implemented a zoning amendment to improve flood resiliency in flood-prone neighborhoods (Watson, 2019). However, coordinated regional efforts are continuously hampered by data accessibility or availability challenges. In addition to gaining basic access to zoning data, standardization of zoning ordinances is needed to facilitate the assessment of patterns and regional trends. Our framework represents one approach to standardization among several possibilities (e.g., Bronin & Ilyankou, 2021), aimed at enabling regional-scale comparisons and informing decision-making.

5. Conclusions

Zoning, as a fundamental tool for promoting economic growth, improving community health and livability, and protecting the natural environment through land use regulations, faces substantial challenges due to the absence of standardization and limited accessibility of data. These challenges hinder the ability to conduct regional-scale assessments and coordinate resilience planning efforts at the local- to regional-scale. In response, we developed a Hierarchical Random Forest algorithm to predict zoning districts over a large geographic extent, specifically the U.S. State of North Carolina. Our findings demonstrate high accuracy in predicting zoning districts for counties with partially available training data. However, we observed limitations in accurately predicting districts for counties with inaccessible data. Notably, this study represents the first—to the best of our knowledge— attempt to predict zone districts state-wide. We have made the complete workflow, data, and code openly available to facilitate future updates, further validation, and application of the framework to wide-ranging issues from the impacts of zoning in North Carolina to the implications of zoning for housing affordability and resiliency planning.

Data and Code Accessibility

The data that support the findings of this study are accessible on Zenodo with the identifier [masked for blind review]. All scripts and workflows are available on GitHub at [masked for blind review].

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge financial support by the U.S. Geological Survey Southeast Climate Adaptation Science Center (award G19AC00083), North Carolina Sea Grant (award R/MG-2209), and U.S. Department of Agriculture McIntire-Stennis Capacity Grant program. The authors also thank all counties and municipalities that shared their zoning data and the Town of Leland Community Development Department for Planning and Zoning for feedback on the usability and applicability of our data framework for long-term planning and adaptation purposes.

Data and code accessibility

The data that support the findings of this study are accessible on Zenodo with the identifier <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8136886>. All scripts and workflows are available on GitHub at <https://github.com/malawrim/Spatially-Complete-Zoning-Maps>.

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